

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/mcz
hash://md5/620281694216487fe9f053c596b7f00a

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2026-06-03

Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/mcz, has fingerprint hash://md5/620281694216487fe9f053c596b7f00a, is 3.37GiB in size and contains 28,249 interactions with 10 unique types of associations (e.g., adjacentTo) between 4,474 primary taxa (e.g., *Gasterosteus aculeatus* Linnaeus, 1758) and 4,810 associated taxa (e.g., ground). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University - Version
162.515 <https://digir.mcz.harvard.edu/ipt/archive.do?r=mczbase>
2026-06-02T17:03:45.411Z hash://md5/620281694216487fe9f053c596b7f00a

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11

tool name	version
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 3.37GiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/mcz

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/mcz \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/mcz \
  > interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/mcz \
  | nomer append col \
  > name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/mcz`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/mcz`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/mcz`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/mcz`)

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/mcz`, has fingerprint hash://md5/620281694216487fe9f053c596b7f00a, is 3.37GiB in size and contains 28,249 interactions with 10 unique types of associations (e.g., `adjacentTo`) between 4,474 primary taxa (e.g., *Gasterosteus aculeatus* Linnaeus, 1758) and 4,810 associated taxa (e.g., `ground`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Tropidonophis montanus (Lidth De Jeude, 1911) (Lidth De Jeude, 1911)	eats	MCZ:Herp:A-92499	http://mczbase.mcz.harvard.edu/guid/MCZ:Herp:142425
Lithobates catesbeianus (Shaw, 1802)	eats	MCZ:Herp:R-200746	http://mczbase.mcz.harvard.edu/guid/MCZ:Herp:109076
Lithobates catesbeianus (Shaw, 1802)	eats	MCZ:Herp:R-200745	http://mczbase.mcz.harvard.edu/guid/MCZ:Herp:109076
Pyxicephalus adspersus	interactsWith	duplicates of MCZ-A-20225 - 20228 are given new catalog numbers MCZ-A-154068 - 154070 02OCT2023 Tsuyoshi Takahashi	http://mczbase.mcz.harvard.edu/guid/MCZ:Herp:20227

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
adjacentTo	12355
hasHost	8011
interactsWith	7633
visitsFlowersOf	93
parasiteOf	75
eats	55
visits	16
hasParasite	8
eatenBy	2
killedBy	1

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Gasterosteus aculeatus Linnaeus, 1758	1142
Perdita sp. Smith, 1853	1054
Xylocopa darwini Cockerell, 1926	609
Tympanogaster robinae Perkins 2006	573
Pardosa moesta Banks, 1892	415
Gymnochthebius setosus Perkins 2005	376
Tympanogaster megamorpha Perkins 2006	372
Tympanogaster magarra Perkins 2006	358
Pheidole sp. Westwood, 1839	343
Tympanogaster moondarra Perkins 2006	327
Subdoluseps bowringii (Günther, 1864) (Günther, 1864)	311
Schizocosa communis (Emerton, 1885)	283
Camponotus sp. Mayr, 1861	278
Tympanogaster wooloomgabba Perkins 2006	260
Pardosa xerampelina (Keyserling, 1877)	225
Tympanogaster modulatrix Perkins 2006	210
Symbion americanus Obst, Funch & Kristensen, 2006	208
Tympanogaster schizolabra (Deane 1933)	208
Gymnochthebius lividus (Deane 1933)	198

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
ground	2449
ex. bare rocks in splash zone	2179
ground in pitfall trap	2032
wood panels	837
karst	485
ex wet films along margin of rills	236
flowing over smooth mudstone. Wet sclerophyll forest (Eucalyptus regnans)	
Mites	228
Ceanothus	182
ex muddy margins of undercut creek banks near water level	178
ex. bare rocks in stream	177
tree	174

targetTaxonName	count
Stylopized	172
ex. human dung	169
ground and trees	167
ex rotten log	165
surface of ground	160
silty sand and sand along margins of gravelly 'semi-urban' creek	160
ex. leaf/twig debris in streambed pools	158
hygropetric habitats at edge of pool at base of waterfall and associated seeps	148

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Tympanogaster robinae Perkins 2006	hasHost	ex. bare rocks in splash zone	573
Tympanogaster magarra Perkins 2006	hasHost	ex. bare rocks in splash zone	358
Tympanogaster moondarra Perkins 2006	hasHost	ex. bare rocks in splash zone	324
Pardosa moesta Banks, 1892	adjacentTo	ground in pitfall trap	301
Tympanogaster wooloomgabba Perkins 2006	hasHost	ex. bare rocks in splash zone	260
Tympanogaster megamorpha Perkins 2006	hasHost	ex wet films along margin of rills flowing over smooth mudstone. Wet sclerophyll forest (Eucalyptus regnans)	218

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Neoantistea magna (Keyserling, 1887)	adjacentTo	ground	193
Schizocosa communis (Emerton, 1885)	adjacentTo	ground	183
Tympanogaster precariosa Perkins 2006	hasHost	ex. bare rocks in stream	172
Tympanogaster aldinga Perkins 2006	hasHost	ex. bare rocks in splash zone	170
Xylocopa darwini Cockerell, 1926	interactsWith	Mites	167
Gymnochthebius setosus Perkins 2005	adjacentTo	silty sand and sand along margins of gravelly 'semi-urban' creek	153
Tympanogaster schizolabra (Deane 1933)	interactsWith	hygropetric habitats at edge of pool at base of waterfall and associated seeps	148
Anadenobolus pedernales Pérez-Asso, 2004	adjacentTo	karst	146
Tympanogaster pagetae Perkins 2006	hasHost	ex. bare rocks in splash zone	145
Gymnochthebius setosus Perkins 2005	hasHost	ex muddy margins of undercut creek banks near water level	144
Tympanogaster novicia (Blackburn 1896)	hasHost	ex. bare rocks in splash zone at side of waterfall	140
Perdita sp. Smith, 1853	interactsWith	Heterotheca	136

Pardosa distincta (Blackwall, 1846)	adjacentTo	ground in pitfall trap	135
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Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download `svg`

You can download the indexed dataset under review at `indexed-interactions.csv.gz`. A tab-separated file can be found at `indexed-interactions.tsv.gz`

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```

MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"
  
```


Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

```

METADATA
  "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
  "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
  "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
  "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
END
CLASS
  STYLE
    COLOR          232 232 232
    OUTLINECOLOR  32 32 32
  END
END
LAYER
  NAME "indexed-interactions"
  TYPE POLYGON
  STATUS ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
  CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
  DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
      DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 3.6044420662607233
      RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
  END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Triungulin	NONE	col	Triungulin
Pungitius	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Pungitius
Salmonids	NONE	col	Salmonids
High plants	NONE	col	High plants

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	2939
col	class	8
col	family	144
col	form	1
col	genus	773
col	infraorder	1
col	kingdom	1
col	order	9
col	phylum	3

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	species	3895
col	subfamily	8
col	subgenus	26
col	suborder	1
col	subspecies	143
col	superfamily	1
col	tribe	2
col	variety	6
discoverlife	NA	7539
discoverlife	species	370
gbif	NA	3029
gbif	class	7
gbif	family	143
gbif	genus	784
gbif	kingdom	2
gbif	order	9
gbif	phylum	3
gbif	species	3806
gbif	subspecies	143
gbif	variety	16
itis	NA	4288
itis	class	6
itis	family	136
itis	genus	653
itis	infraorder	1
itis	kingdom	1
itis	order	9
itis	phylum	3
itis	species	2700
itis	subclass	2
itis	subfamily	7
itis	suborder	1
itis	subspecies	90
itis	superfamily	1
itis	tribe	1
itis	variety	13
mdd	NA	7908
ncbi	NA	4680
ncbi	class	8
ncbi	family	134
ncbi	genus	687
ncbi	infraorder	2
ncbi	order	9
ncbi	phylum	3

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
ncbi	series	1
ncbi	species	2327
ncbi	subclass	1
ncbi	subfamily	7
ncbi	subgenus	18
ncbi	subspecies	48
ncbi	superfamily	1
ncbi	tribe	1
ncbi	varietas	2
pbdb	NA	7049
pbdb	class	9
pbdb	family	118
pbdb	genus	393
pbdb	informal	1
pbdb	infraorder	1
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	order	9
pbdb	phylum	3
pbdb	species	317
pbdb	subclass	1
pbdb	subfamily	4
pbdb	suborder	2
pbdb	superfamily	1
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	tribe	2
pbdb	unranked clade	1
tpt	NA	7346
tpt	family	3
tpt	genus	52
tpt	species	507
wfo	NA	7379
wfo	family	5
wfo	genus	185
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	326
wfo	subspecies	6
wfo	variety	9
worms	NA	6371
worms	class	7
worms	family	107
worms	genus	443
worms	infraorder	1
worms	kingdom	1
worms	order	9

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	phylum	3
worms	species	950
worms	subclass	1
worms	subfamily	2
worms	suborder	1
worms	subspecies	13
worms	superfamily	1
worms	variety	1

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	3957
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5010
col	SYNONYM_OF	1432
discoverlife	NONE	8876
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	347
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	119
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	27
gbif	NONE	4046
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	5169
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	1307
itis	NONE	5354
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3626
itis	SYNONYM_OF	314
mdd	NONE	9099
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	103
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	5
ncbi	NONE	5767
ncbi	SAME_AS	3356
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	173
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	6
pbdb	NONE	8173
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	989
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	98
tpt	NONE	8597

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	84
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	694
wfo	NONE	8612
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	481
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	70
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	164
worms	NONE	7481
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1606
worms	SYNONYM_OF	268

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T12:26:39Z	note	found unresolved reference [MCZ:Cryo:16616]
2026-06-03T12:26:39Z	note	found unresolved reference [MCZ:Cryo:16620]
2026-06-03T12:26:39Z	note	found unresolved reference [MCZ:Cryo:16628]
2026-06-03T12:26:39Z	note	found unresolved reference [MCZ:Cryo:16629]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
found unresolved reference [MCZ:Cryo:16616]	1
found unresolved reference [MCZ:Cryo:16620]	1
found unresolved reference [MCZ:Cryo:16628]	1
found unresolved reference [MCZ:Cryo:16629]	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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